

Planning for Succession as a Trigger for Change: Insights from the Farmer Intention Survey

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Summary

Context:

- 63% of Scottish Farmers are aged 55 and above (June Agricultural Census 2023)
- The total number of farmers and crofters in Scotland is close to 45,000 in 2023 (June Agricultural Census 2023)
- Findings presented here are from the Farmer Intention Survey 2018, a representative sample of 2,494 Scottish farmers, of which 317 (around 15%) were crofters.

Path Dependency

- 'No change' is by far the most common response amongst farmers and crofters to recent and anticipated future changes; this indicates strong path dependency within the industry.

Planning for succession (PFS):

- About half of farmers and crofters who responded had identified successors; a fifth indicated that 'it is too early to say'.
- Larger farms are more likely to have identified successors than smaller farms

PFS is associated with increases in technology and diversification in the past 5 years

- Farmers who have identified successors were more likely to report increases in:

↑ investment in new technologies	↑ investment in tourism
↑ capital investment	↑ size of operation
↑ diversification	↑ land rented
↑ intensity of production	↑ employed labour

PFS is associated with intended technological investment and environmental action in next 5 years

- In the next five years, farmers and crofters who have identified successors are statistically more likely to plan to increase:

↑ investment in new technologies	↑ investment in tourism
↑ capital investment	↑ small-scale woodland
↑ agri-environmental activity	↑ off-farm investment
↑ diversification	↑ employed labour
↑ intensity of production	↑ land rented

Implications

- Supporting succession processes (e.g. through targeted supports, including advice and financial planning) may have the potential to increase levels of innovation and environmental management in Scottish agriculture.

1.0 Introduction

The agricultural sector in Scotland is susceptible to a number of challenges, including but not limited to climate change, biodiversity loss, post-covid recovery, changes in food preferences and population growth. Addressing these challenges will require major changes to farming and crofting practices. The Triggering Change Model highlights that land-based businesses tend to be ‘path dependent’ - following a steady trajectory whereby minor changes may occur incrementally over time, and major changes are made in response to major events, or triggers (Sutherland, 2012). Such trigger events can include financial imperatives, policy alterations, disease outbreaks or farmer succession, amongst many others. This policy brief is concerned with this final trigger event - farmer succession - and uses the Farmer Intention Survey 2018 data to explore how identifying a successor influences on-farm decision making and practice in Scotland.

1.1 The Triggering Change Model

Sutherland et al. (2012) developed a conceptual framework to explain how change is triggered in farmer decision-making, based on a series of UK research studies on agri-environmental behaviour. These studies demonstrated that change in farming trajectories often results from major events. The Triggering Change Model is based on social psychology theory, particularly Petty and Cacioppo’s (1986) Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM). The ELM posits that most decisions are made automatically, with very little active reflection. These decisions tend to lead to minor shifts in behaviour, which are informed by peer groups and the actions or advice of respected others. Major changes to behaviour occur more rarely but are accompanied by active processing of alternatives – individuals actively weigh up their options and seek new knowledge to address particular problems, needs or opportunities. If an identified behavioural shift appears to have potential, the decision-maker begins the process of testing and implementing the new opportunity. Businesses are particularly vulnerable during this time, as new investments in infrastructure and knowledge are being made. If the alteration is successful, the new behaviour is likely to become path dependent, that is, part of standard practice. If it is unsuccessful in some respect, then it is modified, or other options evaluated.

The implications of the Triggering Change Model are that there are specific windows of opportunity for influencing change, pertinent with consideration to the many challenges and necessity for change within farming. These windows of change accompany specific trigger events, which can occur at farm level (e.g. the introduction or loss of a successor) or within the wider system (e.g. reform of subsidies, disease outbreak, market changes).

Konečná and Sutherland, 2022

1.2 Farmer Succession

Succession refers to the legal transmission of the farm management and its inheritance from current managers to the next generation. It can represent a delicate period in the farm life cycle, and a global trend of decreasing intergenerational succession is being observed (Dudek et al, 2022). This trend may be concerning, given the adoption of more sustainable and innovative practices is required to future-proof farming, and that the adoption of such practices is inversely correlated with farmer age (Serebrennikov et al, 2020).

In relation to the Triggering Change Model, land managers who are seeking to enrol a successor can be expected to actively consider options to expand the business. Existing literature has shown planning for and actual farm succession to be related with several differences in land-management. For instance, Barnes et al. (2022) show that having a succession plan is linked to higher persistent efficiency of farms in Scotland; Sottomayer et al (2011) show that the probability of having a successor is positively correlated to on-farm diversification. Inwood & Sharp (2012) highlight that the absence of a successor may lead to disinvestment and passive management style.

However, unlike many other triggers for change in farming, succession will not affect specific groups of farmers simultaneously; its occurrence is steady, ongoing and perhaps less likely to be influenced by external events. For instance, some of the respondents in the Triggering Change paper by Sutherland et al. (2012) converted to organic farming following the BSE outbreak in the UK: the incident made them question how they were treating their livestock. Conversely, farmer succession and the on-farm changes it introduces may be more influenced by farmer age, than external events or pressures.

Therefore, insight into past data surrounding succession may be useful to inform proactive policy initiatives which target this transitional period, to further encourage changes in practice which address the challenges facing the industry.

2.0 Data

The Farmer Intentions Survey is a telephone-based survey of Scottish farmers, crofters and smallholders which was conducted over the summer of 2018. A spatially representative sample of 11,000 businesses was selected using information from the Scottish Government's June Agricultural Census (JAC) stratified by region, business size and farm type. The JAC sampling framework was the most appropriate as it gave national coverage and detailed information on agricultural activity, and it meant that background information requirements from farmers and crofters were minimised. As the JAC is conducted at an agricultural holding level the data was aggregated (where appropriate) to business level, in order to ensure the sampling framework was as representative of Scottish agriculture as possible. A total of 2,494 farmers, crofters and smallholders completed the survey.

Planning for succession was established by responses to the question: 'Have you identified a potential successor who will eventually take over the management of your farm?'. Farmers were grouped based on their response:

- 1137 (49.7%) farmers **planning for succession (PFS)**: those who had identified a potential successor who would eventually take over the management of their farm.
- 697 (30.5%) farmers **not planning for succession (NPFS)**: those who had not identified a potential successor who would eventually take over the management of their farm.
- 454 (19.8%) farmers who found it **too early to say (TETS)**: those who could not confirm either way.

The relationship between succession planning and farmer behaviour was analysed by exploring the similarities and differences between these three groups in their responses to a further 28 questions relating to changes made in the farm in the past 5 years and intended changes in the next 5 years.

3.0 Key findings

3.1 Demographics and farm characteristics

Statistics are presented for the three types of farmers (those in the PFS, NPFS, and TETS groups) with a focus on farm and farmer characteristics, specifically, gender, age and Standard Labour Requirements (SLR; proxy for farm size). Overall, the sample was mostly male (1726 out of those who responded to the succession question), with the highest percentage (78.1%) amongst those not planning for succession.

As expected, older farmers were more likely to have identified successors:

- Amongst those farmers aged 40 and under (150 out of those who responded to the question): 26% farmers were planning for succession, 31.3% not planning for succession and 42.7% found it too early to say.
- Amongst those farmers aged 40-54 (617 out of those who responded to the question): 36.3% farmers were planning for succession, 33.9% not planning, and 29.8% found it too early to say.
- Amongst those farmers aged 55 and over (1511 out of those who responded to the question): 57.2% were planning for succession, 29.2% not planning, and 13.6% found it too early to say.

Figure 1: Age distribution of farmers and different attitudes to succession in FIS 2018. TETS=Too early to say; NPFS=Not planning for succession; PFS=planning for succession.

Smaller farms were least likely to have successors: SLR below 3 (1245 out of those who responded to the question): 44.5% were planning for succession, 35.7% were not planning for succession, and 19.8% found it too early to say.

- On crofts (284 out of those who responded to the question): 51.4% of them had plans for succession, followed by 29.2% who didn't and 19.4% who found it too early to say.
- On larger farms (SLR 3 and above; 1043): 55.9% were planning for succession, 24.3% were not planning for succession, and 19.8% found it too early to say.

3.2 Changes in the farm and association with succession plans

The following statistics focus on the farm changes that respondents made in the previous five years (2013-2018) and those they intended to make in the next five years (2018-23). Statistical tests (chi-squared tests) were used to assess whether there were meaningful differences between groups according to succession planning status. Farmers in the survey were asked whether they had changed or intended to change 13 types of farm activity and the size of their operation, in the previous and the next five years. Response categories were intention to increase, decrease or not change the activity; farmers who indicated that the activity was not applicable to them were not included in this analysis.

There were eight farm changes significantly associated with succession planning: farmers and crofters with identified successors were statistically more likely to have increased *capital investment, diversification, employed labour, intensity of production, investment in tourism, land rented, new technologies* and *size of operation* (see Figure 2). There were no associations between succession planning and past changes in the amount of land let to or contract farmed by others, the area of forestry, agri-environmental activity, off-farm activity, small scale woodland, and renewable energy.

To give an indication of the scale of the differences between groups, those who stated they were planning for succession were 40% more likely to have increased investment in new technologies, and 90% more likely to have increased investment in tourism, than those who were not planning for succession.

Figure 2: Summary of farm changes made by farmers in 2013-2018 in relation to succession plans.

PFS: planning for succession, TETS: too early to say, NPFS: not planning for succession. Note that bars are scaled to 100% of respondents in each farmer group. Differences between groups are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3 shows the *intended changes* for which there were statistically significant differences based on PFS status. PFS was not associated with intended changes in the amount of land let to or contract farmed by others, the area of forestry and the intensity of production.

In both figures and for all groups, 'No change' responses were the most common for most activities, indicating path dependence. This was followed closely by intentions to increase.

Planning for succession is statistically significant for both past and intended changes: capital investment, diversification, employed labour, investment in tourism, land rented, new technologies, and size of operation all differed significantly depending on responses to the succession question.

PFS is associated with intended technological investment and environmental action in the next 5 years: agri-environmental activity, renewable energy production, small-scale woodland and off-farm investment were all significantly associated to the succession grouping, with those not planning for succession least likely to report intended increases in activities. Renewable energy production was

the only activity that farmers planning for succession were more likely to report than those who found it too early to say (29.6% vs 28.1%).

Figure 3: Summary of intended farm changes for 2018-2023 by farmers and crofters in relation to succession plans

PFS: planning for succession, TETS: too early to say, NPFS: not planning for succession. Note that bars are scaled to 100% of respondents in each farmer group. Differences between groups are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

In general, those who reported it as ‘too early to say’ were as likely or more likely than those planning for succession to report increasing activities. This finding appears to be driven by younger respondents. Out of the 454 farmers who found it too early to say who their successor is, most of the over 55s had not made changes while most of the under 55s had increased capital investment and investment in new technologies and were more likely than older groups to have increased other types of activities. The intended changes showed a similar picture for the over 55s who overall reported no intended changes. The responses were more variable amongst the under 55s, with most of them either reporting increases (notably for diversification, investment in tourism and new technologies), or no intended changes.

4.0. Conclusion

Findings demonstrate that farmers and crofters who are planning for succession are more likely to invest in their businesses for a number of years prior to formal succession taking place. Supports aimed at this period in farm and croft transition have the potential to facilitate transformational change, since succession planning can represent a key trigger point for change in farm businesses. Younger farmers and crofters are also more likely to be making and planning changes to their activities.

Notably, recent investments (2013-2018 reference period) emphasise new technology and capital investment, as well as tourism and farm diversification. Plans for the forthcoming reference period (2018-2023) also included more agri-environmental activity, small-scale woodland creation, and renewable energy production. This suggests an awareness amongst future farmers and crofters of the importance of environmental care to the viability of the farm and achievement of government targets. Ensuring generational renewal has an important part to play in achieving these objectives and the long-term viability of the agricultural sector.

Findings thus support the contention that interventions which facilitate on-farm succession may have potential to promote both business viability and environmental activity. Financial planning can be expensive. Succession is also a sensitive process, sometimes requiring professional mediation between family members. Study findings demonstrate that there are farmers of all ages – up to 75+, who still believe it is ‘too early to say’ whether their farm will have a successor. Farmers and crofters often continue to farm well into their 70s and 80s and may be unwilling to hand over the reins of the farm – or give up their identity as a farmer (Riley 2016) – when they themselves may not have inherited the farm until they were in their 60s. Senior farmers may also have limited pension provisions or housing options beyond their current on-farm residence, making the option of retirement off the farm unfeasible. Supports which normalise succession planning at earlier ages and facilitate its success may help to increase the innovation and environmental actions characteristic of Scotland’s agriculture sector. Future research should aim to assess potential interventions to support succession and their effect on the sector’s sustainability.

5.0 References

- Barnes, A. P., McMillan, J., Sutherland, L. A., Hopkins, J., Thomson, S. G. (2022). Farmer intentional pathways for net zero carbon: Exploring the lock-in effects of forestry and renewables. *Land Use Policy*, 112, 105861.
- Dudek, M., & Pawłowska, A. (2022). Can succession improve the economic situation of family farms in the short term? Evidence from Poland based on panel data. *Land Use Policy*, 112, 105852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105852>
- Inwood, S., & Sharp, J. S. (2012). Farm persistence and adaptation at the rural–urban interface: Succession and farm adjustment. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 28(1), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2011.07.005>
- Konečná, M.M. & Sutherland, L-A. (2022). Digital innovations in the Czech Republic: developing the inner circle of the Triggering Change Model. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension* 28: 577-600. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2022.2039247>
- Riley, M. (2016). Still Being the ‘Good Farmer’: (Non-)retirement and the Preservation of Farming Identities in Older Age. *Sociologia Ruralis* 56: 96-115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12063>
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. In *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology* (pp. 123–205). [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2601\(08\)60214-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2601(08)60214-2)
- R Core Team (2023). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Scottish Government (2023). Results from the Scottish Agricultural Census: June 2023. [Results from the Scottish Agricultural Census: June 2023 - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](https://www.gov.scot/resources/publications/2023/06/230601-scottish-agricultural-census-june-2023/)
- Serebrennikov, D., Thorne, F., Kallas, Z., & McCarthy, S. (2020). Factors influencing adoption of sustainable farming practices in Europe: A Systemic review of Empirical literature. *Sustainability*, 12(22), 9719. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229719>
- Sottomayor, M., Tranter, R., & Costa, L. (2011). Likelihood of succession and farmers’ attitudes towards their future behaviour: evidence from a survey in Germany, the United Kingdom and Portugal. *International Journal of the Sociology of Agriculture and Food*, 18(2), 121–133. <https://doi.org/10.48416/ijsaf.v18i2.250>
- Sutherland, L-A., Burton, R.J.F., Ingram, J., Blackstock, K., Slee, B., Gotts, N. (2012). Triggering change : Towards a conceptualisation of major change processes in farm decision-making. *Journal of Environmental Management* 104, 142-151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.03.013>

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